

MECHANISMS OF FRACTURE IN MG-ALLOYS AND COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY CONVENTIONAL FABRICATION ROUTES

K.Purazrang and P.Abachi
Metallurgical Eng. Department,
Sharif University of Technology, Tehran/Iran

ABSTRACT

The light-metal composites are attractive to industries concerned about weight saving e.g. carmakers. The combination of Al₂O₃ or SiC in the form of fibers, whiskers, particulates, etc. with the light-metal alloys provide structural materials of the superior specific mechanical properties such as high strength and stiffness with excellent wear resistance. However, wherever the application of components requires an acceptable ductility and toughness the employment of MMC's encounters limitations. Recent studies on fracture toughness of Mg-alloys composites indicated on relative low fracture toughness. However in any particular case before employment of any investigation for the improvement of the toughness properties, it is of interest to know and understand the mechanisms of fracture.

In this work the mechanisms of fracture, in Mg-alloys and composites, have been studied. The microscopic examination of fracture specimens in the light and scanning electron microscope (SEM) indicated on different fracture mechanisms depending on Mg-alloy microstructure, kind of reinforcement and obviously on fabrication-routes.

INTRODUCTION

With help of metallurgical strengthening techniques metallic materials have already obtained their ultimate mechanical properties. However, high performance technology demands structural materials of higher specific strength and stiffness. Metal matrix composites based on light metals such as aluminium and magnesium provide a number of modern technological requirements which make them promising materials for future applications. The mechanical tests of metal matrix composites generally indicate lower tensile ductility as well as lower fracture toughness compared with wrought alloys. Therefore, the applications of MMC's have had some limitations. Obviously the widespread useful application of MMC's depends on the improvement of their fracture toughness behaviour thus in this connexion the understanding of the crack initiation and

crack propagation mechanisms in composites seems to be necessary in order to use metallurgical processes, which may improve the fracture properties.

The fracture mechanisms of alloys have been the subject of a number of studies [1-4]. Depending on the microstructure of alloys, the fracture may initiate and grow with voids which nucleate at particles. In the case of the matrix containing particles, the cavities may also form at the interface between the particle and matrix and also by fracture of the brittle inclusions. It is generally accepted that the normal stress across the particle or particle-matrix interface has to reach a critical value prior to void formation [5]. When voids nucleate then they grow with increasing strain and combine finally to fracture the matrix [6,7]. One of the main differences between the alloys and MMC's construction is due to the fact that the reinforcements in MMC's are of different size, shape and distribution compared with the particles in alloys. In addition the volume fraction of reinforcement, interfacial strengths of the reinforcement/matrix interface and the kind of reinforcement have to be considered. The study of failure processes in MMC's, therefore, requires close observations of interactions between an initiated crack, the reinforcement, matrix and the matrix/reinforcement interface. Particles larger than 1 μm but less than 100 μm in diameter may alter the slip characteristic of the matrix alloy by blocking the slip lines [8,9]. There may also be secondary effect, such as limiting the operation of secondary dislocation sources and the extent of cross slip. These limitations lead to decrease the size of plastic zone surrounding a crack tip, which may be the most important effect of particles on changing the fracture mechanisms in MMC's. It has been also suggested that the voids formation may be facilitated by prior damage of particles [10,11]. The high stress concentration and strain ahead of a sharp crack tip lead to fracture the particles so that voids nucleate at very low applied strains. The failure occurs when a critical strain is achieved to allow voids to grow between damaged particles. The voids formation may be due to the development of a small-scale plastic zone in front of the sharp crack tip when it is loaded [12]. The plastic zone which was generated as a result of the crack opening displacement interacts with the microstructure so that the plastic flow concentrates around the embedded particles. In the course of the formation of the process zone the voids nucleate at the ends of the particles. The voids formed in front of the crack continue to grow and in an appropriate stress-strain state at the crack tip the coalescence of the voids leads to form a crack propagation. So, in this procedure the small scale yielding of the matrix in front of the crack tip is the condition for the formation of the plastic zone which leads to create the voids at the ends of the particles. This is in agreement with the concept that the fracture initiation process is strain controlled [13].

In the case of fibrous composites the fracture mechanisms are rather complicated. Depending upon the conditions of the composite such as the ductility of the matrix, interfacial energy of fibre/matrix interface and the length of the fibre the process of fracture may be involved with plastic deformation, debonding of the fibre/matrix interface, fibre pull out, fibre damage and crack branching [14-16]. A large plastic deformation may also occur in the ductile matrix of composite, near a loaded crack tip, which has an important influence on the fracture-toughness and fracture mechanisms. However, the unique influence of the interfacial properties on fracture processes have to be particularly considered. Corresponding to the interfacial energy of fibre/matrix interface either a strong or a weak bonding may be formed which can

have great effects on the occurring of various damages. This is because of the importance of debonding and fibre pull-out on fracture of composite materials. In a composite of ductile matrix the debonding of the loaded fibre and matrix is unusual. That is, the shear stress resisting the fibre movement equalizes the shear strength of the matrix. However in the composites with the fibre length below the critical length, given in Eqn (1) :

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_{fu}}{2\tau} d \quad (1)$$

τ is shear strength of either matrix or the interface, σ_{fu} is the fibre tensile strength and d is the fibre diameter, fracture may occur by the fibre pull-out. The fibre fracture may also occur by a fibre of a length greater than l_c . In a composite of rather brittle matrix, debondings along the fibre/matrix interfaces may occur and the fibre can be pulled out of the matrix when the debonding process is completed. Therefore the fracture of the fibrous composite may be the result of several mechanisms which seldom occur independently from one another. The mechanisms that contribute to the fracture of a composite may occur simultaneously or consecutively.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In the present studies both powder metallurgical as well as squeeze casting techniques are employed to produce magnesium alloys composites. For the P/M technique magnesium alloy AZ91 (8.5–9.5% Al, 0.45–0.9% Zn, 0.15–0.3% Mn, 0.20% Si, 0.01% Ni, balance Mg) of 63 μm maximum size was mixed with silicon carbide particles of 6 μm diameter. The blends were placed in cans, cold and hot pressed and then extruded to the rod of one meter length and 20 mm diameter [17].

Squeeze casting methods were employed to produce magnesium matrix composites with discontinuous alumina fibres. The δ - alumina fibres of 3 μm mean diameter and length of <150 μm were first moulded into the desired shape (perform dimensions: 110.110.35 mm^3). This preform was then heated and placed in a preheated die. The molten magnesium alloy QE22 (0.6% Zr, 2.5% Ag, 2.0% RE, balance Mg) was then introduced into the die and pressure applied by an upper punch [18,19]. The silicon carbide particles and alumina fibres fractions for all composites were set to 5,10 and 15 vol.% . Under the same P/M and Sq/C technique conditions unreinforced magnesium alloys matrices in rods and plates were also manufactured for comparison tests. The short rod method of measuring fracture toughness was used [20]. The short rod specimens of controlled fracture tests, which were used to explanation the micromechanisms of crack propagation, were stopped and unloaded just prior to unstable crack growth. These specimens were then sectioned perpendicular to the slot of the short rod. The crack paths were carefully studied by means of optical and scanning electron microscopy. The fracture surfaces of the fractured specimens were also examined by SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fracture toughness at room temperature were carried out for the P/M and Sq/C materials. The results of fracture toughness of the unreinforced alloys and

composites up to 15 vol.% of reinforcement are shown in figure 1. While the fracture toughness of Sq/C QE22 alloy decreases appreciably with increasing volume fraction of Al₂O₃ short fibres, the fracture toughness of the P/M AZ91 alloy is nearly unaffected by SiC particles reinforcement. In addition the Sq/C QE22 alloy and composites reveal a higher fracture toughness compared to P/M AZ91 alloy and composites. These may be the result of the distinctions in constructions of alloys and composites produced by P/M and Sq/C procedures. Figure 2 shows an example of a typical section of a short rod specimen of the unreinforced Sq/C QE22 alloy. The fracture test was stopped prior to an unstable crack growth. It can be seen that the crack was initiated at and propagated along the grain boundaries through the precipitates which was identified as an intermetallic compound of Mg₉RE [21]. Figure 3 shows the crack propagation region of figure 2 at higher magnification which was taken by SEM. It seems that the cavities were formed at interfaces between the matrix and precipitates, and the formed crack has fractured the massive precipitates on grain boundaries. Figure 4 shows a SEM fractograph of fractured Sq/C QE22 short rod specimen. The fracture surface consisted of dimples at the grain boundaries, which indicate on voids formation prior to the crack formation. A slightly different crack path was observed by the Sq/C QE22 composites. Figure 5 shows the crack growth in a QE22 + 15 vol.% Al₂O₃ short fibres Sq/C composite. The crack was propagated along the grain boundaries but continued occasionally through the reinforcement. The SEM micrograph of the specimen indicates the crack propagation along the interface between matrix and fibres (figure 6). The reinforcements' fracturing by crack growth can also be observed. Accordingly the reinforcement has a clear effect on fracture mechanisms of Sq/C QE22 alloy composites.

The microscopic examinations of short rod specimens of P/M materials after controlled fracture tests disclosed the influence of fabrication routes on fracture mechanisms. Figure 7 shows the crack propagation in the unreinforced P/M AZ91 alloy. The crack growth is characterized by the decohesion of the boundaries between the elongated powder grains in the extrusion direction. The crack is propagated perpendicular to the loading direction with no evidence of yielding. The weak diffusion bound between the elongated powder grains facilitates crack propagation in the P/M alloy. The decohesions of the boundaries between the elongated powder grains were also observed on the fractographs of fractured short rod specimen (figure 8). No major differences in the fracture mechanisms of the P/M composites have been observed. The optical micrograph of figure 9 shows the same crack propagation-mechanisms in the P/M AZ91 alloy + 15 vol.% SiC particulates composite as by the unreinforced P/M AZ91 alloy. The crack grows along the boundaries of the elongated powder grains and occasionally through the row of SiC particles distributed in the extrusion direction. Again no evidence of matrix yielding was observed. Hence the fracture mechanisms of P/M composites were not affected by the reinforcement and as in the case of the unreinforced P/M alloy it was matrix controlled. In addition, SEM micrograph in figure 10 indicates a removing of some of the SiC particulates during specimens preparation, which may be referred to low interfacial bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement in the P/M composites. The crack path proves the crack propagation of the optical microscopy observations.

SUMMARY

The magnesium alloys AZ91 and QE22 were used to produce metal matrix composites for the experimental studies of fracture related properties. The effects of compositions, the volume fraction of the reinforcement as well as fabrication routes were also considered. In the case of Sq/C QE22 alloy the massive precipitates of Mg9RE intermetallic compound on grain boundaries embrittled the alloy. In the unreinforced alloy the crack was propagated along the grain boundaries. Apparently, the cracks formation were the result of cavities formation at the matrix/precipitates interface as well as on the damaged precipitates. The reinforcement altered the fracture mechanisms. It was shown that in the Sq/C QE22 composites the crack propagated on grain boundaries as well as on the matrix/fibre interfaces and the damaged fibres. Consequently the fracture toughness of Sq/C alloy decreases a lot with increasing vol.% of Al₂O₃ short fibres. Entirely different circumstances were observed by the P/M AZ91 alloy and composites. The fractures of the P/M materials were greatly affected by the fabrication route. The cracks were propagated along the elongated boundaries of the powder grains in the extrusion direction. The same mechanism was also observed by composites. In other words, the SiC particulates reinforcement do not have any effects on the fracture mechanisms of the P/M AZ91 composites. Apparently the weak diffusion bond between the elongated powder grains has promoted the crack path by P/M materials. Therefore the fracture toughnesses of the P/M materials were lower compared with those of Sq/C materials. Because of low or missing effects of SiC particulates on the fracture mechanisms of P/M composites, the fracture toughness values were not considerably affected by the reinforcement. Consequently, according to the results of the above examination, the fracture toughness of the magnesium alloys and composites are influenced by the microstructure as well as by the fabrication routes.

REFERENCES:

- 1 . R.H. Van Stone, T.B. Cox, J.R. Low and J.A. Psioda, *Int. Metall. Rev.*, 30,157 (1985).
- 2 . K.E. Puttick, *Phil. Mag.* 5, 759 (1960).
- 3 . J.Gurland and I.J. Plateau, *Trans. Am. Soc. Metals*, 56, 442 (1963).
- 4 . F.A. Mc Clintock, *Ductility*, Am. Soc. Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, P. 255, (1968).
- 5 . A.S. Argon, J. Im and R. Safoglu, *Metall. Trans.*, 6A, 825 (1975).
- 6 . J. D. Evensen, *Scripta Metall.*, 15, 1131 (1981).
- 7 . G.Le Roy, J.D. Emburg, G. Edwards and M.F. Ashby, *Acta Metall.* 29, P. 1509, (1981).
- 8 . D.L. Davidson, "Metal Matrix Composites: Mechanisms and Properties," Academic Press, PP. 217-233, (1991).
- 9 . K. Tanaka, T. Mori, and T. Nakamura, *Phil. Mag.* 21, 267 (1970).
10. T.J. Doel, M.H. Loretto and P. Bowen, *Composites*, Vol. 24, No. 3, PP.270-274, (1993).

11. T.J. Downes and J.E. King, Composites, Vol. 24, No. 3, PP. 276–281, (1993).
12. C.R. Crowe, R.A. Gray and D.F. Hasson, ICCM V San Diego California, July 30–August 1, PP. 843–866, (1985).
13. J. F. Knott, "Fundamentals of Fracture Mechanics", Butterworth London, (1973).
14. A. Kelly, "Interface Effects and the Work of Fracture of a Fibrous Composite", Proc., Roy. Soc. London, A319, 95 (1973).
15. J. J. Masson, A. Weber, M. Miketta, and K. Schulte, "Optionization of the Processing Parameters and Mechanical Behaviour of a Carbon Fibre Reinforced Aluminium Matrix Composite", 12th Ris., International Symposium on Materials Science, (1991).
16. A. S. Tetelman, "Fracture Processes in Fiber Composite Materials", Composite Materials: Testing and Design, ASTM STP 460, American Society and Materials P. 473, (1969).
17. B.L. Mordike, K.U. Kainer and J. Schroeder, "Powder Metallurgical Preparation of Composite Materials." Trans. P MAI 17, PP. 7–17, (1990).
18. K.U. Kainer and B.L. Mordike, "Herstellung und Eigenschaften von Kurzfaserverstaerkten Magnesium Legierungen," Metallurgie 44, PP. 438–443, (1990).
19. K. Purazrang, K.U. Kainer and B.L. Mordike, "Fracture Toughness Behaviour of a Magnesium Alloy Metal–Matrix Composite produced by the Infiltration Technique," Composite 22, PP. 456–462, (1991).
20. L.M. Barker, "A simplified Method for Measuring Plane Strain Fracture Toughness", Eng. Fracture Mech. 9, PP. 361–369, (1977).
21. K.U. Kainer, B.L. Mordike, Metall. 44 Jahrgang., Heft 5., Mai (1990).

Fig.1. Fracture Toughness of Mg-alloys & composites at R.T.

Figs: 2. Showing a typ. sect. of SR. SP. after cont. fracture test of unreinf. Sq/C QE22.
3. A SEM micrograph of fig. 2. It shows crack propagation along the grain boundaries through the Mg9RE precipitates.
4. Showing the fracture surface of a Sq/C QE22 short rod (SR.) specimen.
5. Showing the crack propagation in a Sq/C QE22 + 15 vol.% Al₂O₃ composite.
6. Showing the crack propag. and the reinf. fracturing in a Sq/C QE22 composite.

- Figs: 7 . Showing the crack propagation along the boundaries of the elongated powder grains in the extrusion direction in the unreinforced P/M AZ91 alloy.
- 8 . A SEM fractograph of a P/M AZ91 alloy. It shows the decohesion of the boundaries between the elongated powder grains in the extrusion direction.
- 9 . Showing the crack propagation in P/M AZ91 + 15 vol.% SiC particulates. The crack propagation mechanism is same as by the unreinforced P/M alloy.
- 10 . Showing the removing of the SiC particulate due to low interfacial bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement.